

Effect of aromatic alcohols and carboxylic acids on light induced isomerisation of 1-alkyl-2- $\{(o\text{-thioalkyl})\text{phenylazo}\}$ imidazole

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Abstract : Light irradiated *trans-to-cis* isomerisation of 1-alkyl-2- $\{(o\text{-thioalkyl})\text{phenylazo}\}$ imidazole in presence of phenol, catechol, benzoic acid and salicylic acid (act as *co-factor*) in methanol solution has been studied in this work. The rate of *trans* \rightarrow *cis* photoisomerisation is decreased in presence of co-factor in the medium and is dependent on the concentration of active quotient about photochrome. The decrease in rate follows catechol > benzoic acid > phenol > salicylic acid. This trend is due to the effects of dissociation ability of -O-H/-COOH and intermolecular association of the molecules. The reverse change, *cis-to-trans* is very slow in light irradiation and has been carried out by thermal process at dark. The quantum yield of isomerisation observes same sequence of effects of co-factor as it is seen in case of rate of photoisomerisation.

Keywords : Photochromism, 1-alkyl-2- $\{(o\text{-thioalkyl})\text{phenylazo}\}$ imidazole, co-factors, quantum yield.

Introduction

The photoisomerization of azobenzenes from the *trans* to the *cis* isomer has been carried out by UV light irradiation and back has been switched by visible light or by heating^{1,2}. The more intense absorption at 320 nm corresponds to the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ (S_2 state) transition, and irradiation at this wavelength leads to *trans* \rightarrow *cis* isomerization, whereas the *cis* isomer absorbs at longer wavelengths, around 430 nm, which is due to the $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ (S_1 state) transition inducing *trans* \rightarrow *cis* isomerization. Upon UV irradiation, the distance between the *para* carbon atoms decreases from about 9.0 Å in the *trans* isomer to 5.5 Å in the *cis* form³. This property, azo compounds has been employed for different uses and applications, such as in light controlled polymers⁴, liquid crystals⁵, surface morphology manipulation⁶, and catalysts⁷, and has more recently been found to be promising in controlling the structural and functional changes in biomolecules. Azobenzene derivatives, indeed, have been used for the photoswitching of proteins, like ion channels and receptors, and for the photocontrol of peptides⁸, nucleic acids, lipids, and carbohydrates⁹. The photochromic activity may be varied by

changing the molecule types, presence of substituents, proton donor/acceptor centres different carbocyclic and heterocyclic rings, and also by using coordination with different metal ions. The photochromism of arylazopyridine and their polymers are well known¹⁰⁻¹⁵. In the exploration of other arylazoheterocycle, we use 1-alkyl-2-(arylozo)imidazoles those constitute an interesting class of heterocyclic azo compounds as a potential switching group in biological applications and in coordination chemistry, since imidazole is a ubiquitous and essential group in biology, especially as a metal coordinating site. This family of compounds has been extensively used as ligands in the studies of metal complexes¹⁶⁻²² and some of them are photochromic²³⁻²⁸ in nature. The solution structures, solvent polarity, viscosity, presence of foreign molecules or ions influence the activity of photochromes. In general increase in solvent polarity or use of protic solvents enhances kinetic energy barrier of *cis-trans* isomers²⁹. With this goal we have chosen different proton donor molecules of varying efficiency such as phenol, catechol, benzoic acid and salicylic acid (termed as *co-factors*) and performed photochromism of 1-alkyl-2- $\{(o\text{-thioalkyl})\text{phenyl}$

azo}imidazoles (SRAaiNR', Scheme 1). The co-factor may protonate imidazole-N which will definitely stabilize *trans*-configuration and may affect the rate of photoisomerisation or may influence photoinduced proton transfer (PIPT) process³⁰.

Scheme 1. Isomerization of 1-alkyl-2-*o*-(thioalkyl)phenylazo}-imidazole

Results and discussion

*Photochromism of 1-alkyl-2-*o*-(thioalkyl)phenylazo}imidazole (SRAaiNR')* :

1-Methyl-2-*o*-(thiomethyl)phenylazo}imidazole (SMeaaiNMe), 1-ethyl-2-*o*-(thiomethyl)phenylazo}imidazole (SEtaaiNMe), 1-methyl-2-*o*-(thioethyl)phenylazo}imidazole (SMeaaiNEt) and 1-ethyl-2-*o*-(thioethyl)phenylazo}imidazole (SEtaaiNEt) are used in this work (Scheme 2). Upon irradiation of UV light at λ_{\max} (Table 1) to a methanol solution of SRAaiNR' has shown significant change in the absorption characteristics (Fig. 1). The intense peak at λ_{\max} decreases, which is accompanied by a slight increase at the tail portion of the spectrum around 490 nm until a stationary state is reached. Subsequent

irradiation at the newly appeared longer wavelength peak reverses the course of the reaction and the original spectrum is recovered up to a point, which is another photostationary state under irradiation at the longer wavelength peak. It is observed that upon irradiation with UV light *trans*-to-*cis* photoisomerisation proceeded and the *cis* molar ratio is reached to >90%. The absorption spectra of the *trans*-ligands changed with isosbestic points upon excitation into the *cis*-isomer.

Scheme 2. List of photochromes and co-factors used to influence environment of photochrome.

Fig. 1. Spectral changes of SMeaaiNMe in methanol solution upon repeated irradiation at 363 nm at 3 min interval at 25 °C.

Quantum yields (Table 1) were measured for the *trans*-to-*cis* ($\phi_{t \rightarrow c}$) photoisomerisation of all the compounds in methanol on irradiation of UV wavelength. The $\phi_{t \rightarrow c}$ values are significantly dependent on nature of substituents. The -Me substituent at azoaryl group and alkyl substituent at N(1)-position (1-Me and 1-Et) reduce $\phi_{t \rightarrow c}$ values. In general, increase in mass of the molecule reduces the rate of isomerisation, *trans*-to-*cis*. The quantum yields of the *trans*-to-*cis* photoisomerization were also determined.

Table 1. Excitation wavelength (λ_{π,π^*}), rate of *trans*(t) \rightarrow *cis*(c) conversion and quantum yield ($\phi_{t\rightarrow c}$) of photoisomerisation in presence of different co-factor

Compd.	Co-factor	λ_{π,π^*} (nm)	Isobestic points (nm)	Rate of t \rightarrow c conversion $\times 10^8$ (s $^{-1}$)	$\phi_{t\rightarrow c}$
SMeaaiNMe	Nil	357	337	4.908	0.317
SMeaaiNEt	Do	358	337	3.108	0.232
SEtaaiNMe	Do	357	336	4.670	0.290
SEtaaiNEt	Do	356	335	2.950	0.197
SMeaaiNMe	Phenol	355	329, 501	2.562	0.120
SMeaaiNEt	Do	354	326, 500	1.872	0.085
SEtaaiNMe	Do	355	328, 495	2.629	0.091
SEtaaiNEt	Do	356	327, 502	1.563	0.072
SMeaaiNMe	Catechol	354	340, 492	4.191	0.190
SMeaaiNEt	Do	353	342, 493	3.817	0.170
SEtaaiNMe	Do	355	341, 492	3.679	0.162
SEtaaiNEt	Do	354	344, 494	3.259	0.148
SMeaaiNMe	Benzoic acid	356	333, 498	3.637	0.160
SMeaaiNEt	Do	355	334, 501	3.078	0.141
SEtaaiNMe	Do	354	331, 496	3.011	0.135
SEtaaiNEt	Do	355	333, 499	2.668	0.124
SMeaaiNMe	Salicylic acid	355	334, 519	2.012	0.090
SMeaaiNEt	Do	356	337, 510	1.552	0.071
SEtaaiNMe	Do	354	332, 515	1.712	0.079
SEtaaiNEt	Do	355	333, 511	1.416	0.064

Photochromism of SRAaiNR' in presence of co-factor like phenol, catechol, benzoic acid and salicylic acid :

Photoisomerism is dependent on nature of the molecules, their polarity, rigidity, mass, volume and also on the exterior environment like nature of solvent and its interaction with the photochromic molecules, presence of foreign molecules or ions in the solution and also on the surrounding microenvironments. Molecules may not participate chemically but their non-covalent forces may influence physical, photophysical, catalytic, electrochemical properties. Molecular and supramolecular interactions may regulate photochromic activity of these molecules. π -Donor molecules interact with π -deficient system and has rightly influence the rotor mass and volume and hence, the molecular properties. The spectator molecules or ions (*co-factor*) have selective effect on the photochromic property of SRAaiNR'. The acidic co-factors dissociate in solution and imidazole-N and/or azo-N may be protonated and hence, interact electrostatically with anions obtained from co-factors or present externally in the medium or

with π -electron rich molecules. Azo (-N=N-) is a π -acidic function and increases polarity in the molecule which assists π - π interaction with the molecules and will lead to crowding about the molecule and may affect the *cis-trans* isomerisation. Rate of photoisomerisation changes upon addition of co-factor to azoimidazole in methanol are recorded in Table 1 and a representative spectral change upon addition of benzoic acid to methanol solution of SMeaaiNMe is shown in Fig. 2. The rate of photoisomerisation is reduced in presence of co-factor in the medium and rate is dependent on the concentration of active quotient about photochrome. The co-factor changes the

Fig. 2. Spectral changes of SMeaaiNMe in toluene solution in presence of benzoic acid (1 : 1 mole ratio) upon repeated irradiation at 363 nm at 3 min interval at 25 °C.

rate of *trans* \rightarrow *cis* photoisomerisation and the rate decreases as catechol > benzoic acid > phenol > salicylic acid (Table 1). This trend may be due to the dissociation ability of -O-H/-COOH of co-factor and intermolecular association of the ions. The parameters may control microenvironment of the photochromic function. Catechol (C₆H₄(OH)₂) is more polar than phenol (C₆H₅OH) and hence less soluble in toluene. Thus, local concentration of catechol may be less than phenol in the microenvironment and hence influences weakly to the rate of photoisomerisation of RaaNR'. Benzoic acid exists as dimer in toluene and may approach slowly to orient about the photochromic centre. The conclusion may be drawn from the pK values (pK : phenol, 9.9; catechol, 9.34 and 13.24; benzoic acid, 4.2; salicylic acid, 2.88, 13.56). Thus salicylic acid, being strongest acid amongst four co-

factors, in solution may protonate imidazole-N more actively than others and salicylate ions may also electrostatically orient about $RaaiRH^+$ (Scheme 3). This may increase rotor volume and rotor mass of the photochromic unit. Arylimidazolium ion appears rigidly in *trans*-con-

Scheme 3. Protonation of imidazolyl motif to resist light induced isomerisation.

figuration by intramolecular hydrogen bonding and reduces the rate of isomerisation. In general, increase in mass of the molecule reduces the rate of isomerisation, *trans*-to-*cis*. In presence of co-factors the $\phi_{t \rightarrow c}$ values are significantly less than that of free ligand data (Table 1). The discussion refers to the ground state stability of the co-factors. Benzoic acid is a considerably stronger acid than phenol in the ground state, however in their first excited singlet state the case is just reverse³⁰. Organic base strength also changes considerably upon excitation. Heterocyclic-Ns (nitrogens) are more basic in their excited states than ground state configurations. Under such conditions one expects that proton transfer (PT) in the excited state will be strongly favored from aromatic-OH function. Thus phenol, catechol and salicylic acid will favor protonation to imidazole-N upon irradiation which may cause down fall of rate of *trans* to *cis* isomerisation. Thus protonation acts in the ground state configuration followed by isomerisation upon irradiation i.e. at excited state.

Thermal isomerization, *cis* \rightarrow *trans* :

Long-time UV-light irradiation (~ 360 nm) to the solution has transformed *trans* \rightarrow *cis*-isomer (> 95%) which allows visible light irradiation at 455 nm to transfer to *trans*-isomer slowly. While thermal change at dark is relatively fast (Figs. 3 and 4) and the reaction rate is characterized by a single exponential function. The unimolecular rate constant of the thermal backward isomerization (k) was obtained by the analysis of the measured absorbance,

Fig. 3. The thermal spectral changes of SMEaaiNMe in methanol at 30 °C. Inset figure shows spectra of *cis* and *trans* isomer of SMEaaiNMe.

Fig. 4. The thermal spectral changes of SMEaaiNMe in methanol in presence of benzoic acid (1 : 1 mole ratio) at 30 °C. Inset figure shows spectra of *cis* and *trans* isomer of SMEaaiNMe.

Abs(t), using following equation (eq. (1)).

$$\text{Abs}(t) = (\text{Abs}_Z - \text{Abs}_E)e^{-kt} + \text{Abs}_E \quad (1)$$

The thermal *cis*-to-*trans* isomerisation rates were obtained by monitoring absorption changes intermittently for a *cis*-rich solution kept in the dark at constant temperatures (T) in the range from 298–313 K. The activation energy (E_a) and the frequency factor (A) were obtained from the Arrhenius plot,

$$\ln k = \ln A - E_a/RT$$

where k is the measured rate constant, R is the gas constant and T is temperature. The values of activation free

energy (ΔG^*) and activation entropy (ΔS^*) were obtained through the relationships,

$$\Delta G^* = E_a - RT - T\Delta S^*$$

and

$$\Delta S^* = [\ln A - 1 - \ln(k_B T/h)]/R$$

where k_B and h are Boltzmann's and Plank's constants, respectively.

Where Abs_E and Abs_Z are absorbances corresponding to pure samples of *E*-(*cis*) and *Z*-(*trans*) forms, respectively. The experimental data were fitted by a nonlinear algorithm with eq. (1). The activation energy, E_a , of thermal reverse isomerization was determined by fitting the temperature dependent k values (Fig. 5) and the results are listed in Table 2. The value is substantially lower than that of azobenzene (94.2 kJ mol^{-1})³¹. The faster *cis*-to-*trans* thermal isomerization of SRaaiNR' compared to azobenzene is due to a lower enthalpy factor, since the activation entropy is of a larger negative value.

Fig. 5. The Eyring plots of rate constants of *cis*-to-*trans* thermal isomerisation of SMeaiNMe (b) in (a) salicylic acid, (b) phenol, (c) catechol and (d) benzoic acid medium at different temperatures.

Experimental

Materials :

1-Alkyl-2- $\{(o\text{-thioalkyl})\text{phenylazo}\}$ imidazole were synthesized by reported procedure¹⁶. All other chemicals and solvents were reagent grade as received. Imidazole, 2-aminothiophenol, salicylic acid were of analytical reagent grade collected from SRL, India. Benzoic acid, phenol, catechol were collected from SRL, India.

Physical measurements :

Spectroscopic data were obtained using the following instruments : UV-Vis spectra from Perkin-Elmer Lambda 25 spectrophotometer. Photoexcitation has been carried out using Perkin-Elmer LS-55 spectrofluorimeter.

Photometric measurements :

The experiments are carried out using super dry solvent. Absorption spectra were taken with a Perkin-Elmer Lambda 25 UV/Vis spectrophotometer in a $1 \times 1 \text{ cm}$ quartz optical cell maintained at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The light source of a Perkin-Elmer LS 55 spectrofluorimeter was used as an excitation light, with a slit width of 10 nm . An optical filter was used to cut off overtones when necessary. The absorption spectra of the *cis* isomers were obtained by extrapolation of the absorption spectra of a *cis*-rich mixture for which the composition is known from $^1\text{H NMR}$ integration. Quantum yields (ϕ) were obtained by measuring initial *trans*-to-*cis* isomerization rates (v) in a well-stirred solution within the above instrument using the equation,

$$n = (\phi I_0/V)(1 - 10^{-Abs})$$

where I_0 is the photon flux at the front of the cell, V is the volume of the solution, and Abs is the initial absorbance at the azobenzene ($\phi = 0.11$ for $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ excitation³¹) under the same irradiation condition.

Conclusion

1-Alkyl-2- $\{(o\text{-thioalkyl})\text{phenylazo}\}$ imidazole (SRaaiNR') isomerizes from stable *trans*- to *cis*-isomer on light irradiation at UV wavelength. The reverse, *cis*-to-*trans*, is very slow by light and susceptible to heat. The isomerisation is dependent on microenvironment about the photochrome in solution. Addition of weak H^+ donors like phenol, catechol, benzoic acid and salicylic acid (act as *co-factor*) reduces the rate and quantum yield of the process according to catechol > benzoic acid > phenol > salicylic acid. This trend is due to the effects of dissociation ability of $-\text{O-H}/-\text{COOH}$, the functional group and intermolecular association of the ions. The activation energy of *cis*-to-*trans* is calculated following Arrhenius equation which is less than that of free ligand data. This describes the trafficking of *co-factor* about SRaaiNR' to increase the effective volume of the photochrome which reduces the rate of isomerisation and quantum yield.

Table 2. Rate and activation parameters for *cis* (c) \rightarrow *trans* (t) thermal isomerisation

Compd.	Co-factor	Temp. (K)	Rate of thermal c \rightarrow t conversion $\times 10^5$ (s $^{-1}$)	E_a (kJ mol $^{-1}$)	ΔH^* (kJ mol $^{-1}$)	ΔS^* (J mol $^{-1}$ K $^{-1}$)	ΔG^* (kJ mol $^{-1}$)
SMeaaiNMe	Nil	298	4.329	25.42	22.88	-232.41	93.87
		303	5.295				
		308	6.191				
		313	7.091				
SMeaaiNEt		298	4.614	22.99	20.45	-240.02	93.77
		303	5.598				
		308	6.293				
		313	7.269				
SEtaaiNMe		298	4.425	21.92	19.38	-244.04	93.94
		303	5.123				
		308	5.985				
		313	6.729				
SEtaaiNEt		298	4.625	18.88	16.34	-253.96	93.93
		303	5.123				
		308	5.985				
		313	6.589				
SMeaaiNMe	Phenol	298	4.715	14.49	17.02	-222.94	85.13
		303	5.699				
		308	6.298				
		313	6.565				
SMeaaiNEt		298	4.655	14.33	16.87	-223.37	85.11
		303	5.964				
		308	6.259				
		313	6.569				
SEtaaiNMe		298	4.756	13.78	16.33	-225.08	85.09
		303	5.964				
		308	6.359				
		313	6.599				
SEtaaiNEt		298	4.982	13.15	15.69	-226.99	85.04
		303	5.901				
		308	6.459				
		313	6.759				
SMeaaiNMe	Catechol	298	4.521	17.57	20.11	-213.54	85.24
		303	5.130				
		308	6.210				
		313	6.531				
SMeaaiNEt		298	4.536	17.50	20.05	-213.37	85.23
		303	5.142				
		308	6.231				
		313	6.542				
SEtaaiNMe		298	4.539	17.48	20.02	-213.75	85.23
		303	5.151				
		308	6.236				
		313	6.544				

Table-2 (contd.)

SEtaaiNEt		298	4.543	17.38	19.92	-213.75	85.21
		303	5.156				
		308	6.247				
		313	6.549				
SMeaaiNMe	Benzoic acid	298	4.699	15.65	18.19	-219.46	85.19
		303	5.251				
		308	6.234				
		313	6.551				
SMeaaiNEt		298	4.701	15.54	18.07	-219.65	85.18
		303	5.299				
		308	6.257				
		313	6.555				
SEtaaiNMe		298	4.704	15.56	18.09	-219.59	85.19
		303	5.295				
		308	6.261				
		313	6.560				
SEtaaiNEt		298	4.711	15.47	18.01	-219.87	85.16
		303	5.301				
		308	6.258				
		313	6.560				
SMeaaiNMe	Salicylic acid	298	5.872	12.40	14.95	-228.49	84.75
		303	6.251				
		308	7.109				
		313	7.759				
SMeaaiNEt		298	5.881	12.27	14.82	-228.92	84.74
		303	6.283				
		308	7.111				
		313	7.761				
SEtaaiNMe		298	5.899	12.30	14.84	-228.78	84.74
		303	6.289				
		308	7.179				
		313	7.767				
SEtaaiNEt		298	5.905	11.77	14.32	-230.31	84.67
		303	6.829				
		308	7.183				
		313	7.894				

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